

INTERPRETATION OF PROVERBS IN THE WORKS OF SAID AHMED

Kurbonova Gavkhar Xurramovna

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Kholiyorova Zulfiya

Student of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Said Ahmadning badiiy ijodi, hikoya yozish mahorati, hikoya tili uslublari va badiiy tasvir vositalaridan foydalanish mahorati aks ettirilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Hikoya, badiiy ijod, hikoya qilish, stilistika, til uslubi, badiiy tasvir vositalari.

Аннотация. В этой статье отражены художественное творчество Саида Ахмеда, навыки написания рассказов, стили повествовательного языка и средства художественного изображения.

Ключевые слова: Рассказ, художественное творчество, повествование, стилистика, языковой стиль, средства художественного изображения.

Abstract. This article reflects on Said Ahmed's artistic creativity, story-writing skills, story language styles, and skill in using artistic visual tools.

Key words: Story, artistic creativity, storytelling, stylistics, language style, artistic visual tools.

With his colorful stories, journalistic articles, realistic short stories and novels, Saeed Ahmad occupies a worthy place in modern Uzbek literature. He is especially famous as a master of satire and humor.

The press played an important role in the growth of the writer. He worked in the newspapers "Yosh Leninchi", "Red Uzbekistan", magazines "Mushtum", "Sharq yulduzi", radio committee of Uzbekistan.

Saeed Ahmad was first known as a short story writer. In 1940, his first collection of short stories – "Tortik" - appeared.

Saeed Ahmad calls this collection, which includes many stories, "exercise". But Abdulla Qahhor, who is the teacher of the Youth, strongly criticizes this. He said: "Sayed Ahmed seems to be able to play a proper practice when he picks up a drum, twists his ears, presses the curtain, and clicks, but he has not practiced playing yet. All the stories in "Tortiq" show that. In the story "Ko'klam chechaklari" Saeed Ahmed also shows the thoughts of a patient who was bedridden due to the war (after all, he was a man, he did not want to be bedridden and stare at the ceiling while his wife was

struggling to earn money), his wife's heart expressing the exuberance and springiness of women's feelings, and at the same time loyalty to their family, they can easily find their way to the reader's heart [1].

In the second group of stories, the comic spirit takes the main place. These include the stories of the series “Desert Eagle”, “Desert Winds”, “Hindcha Oyin”, “Kuchukcha”, “Kolbasa qori”, “O‘rik Domla”. The puns, exaggerations and exaggerations characteristic of our people in these stories make the language of the work extremely attractive [2]. In the comic stories of the writer, such as “Stranger”, “Khanka and Tanka”, “My friend Boboev”, vices such as arrogance, provocation, ostentatiousness encountered in life are skillfully exposed. With his small comic works, Said Ahmed founded the amusing theater of miniatures on Uzbek radio and television.

The novel “Ufq”, created in 1964, was the greatest achievement of the second stage of the writer’s creative career. This novel is a trilogy, consisting of parts called “Forty-five days”, “Days of Hijran”, “On the threshold of the horizon”. In it, the artist reflected the heroic labor of the villagers behind the front lines during the war years, the qualities of the Uzbek people, such as generosity and generosity, selflessness and hard work. The novel was so successful that Abdulla Qahhor, who once severely criticized the young writer, positively evaluated the work in 1965 in his article entitled “Inspiration and Skill Effect” as follows: seeing that they had come, we wished that they would be good musicians and play good exercises. This dream is coming true. “Ufq” is an exercise played by him with inspiration and skill.

Said Ahmad’s novel “Ufq” has a special place in Uzbek prose. The story of the construction of the Great Fergana Canal, which was completed in 45 days by the unselfish Uzbek people, the hard work of our people at the front and behind the front during the war years, and the hardships they endured during the post-war recovery period, are expressed in the novel. In our opinion, if there were no events related to the image of Tursunboy in the work, the work would not have differed from the traditional novels created on the military theme in Uzbek literature. Because in “Days of Hijran”

the heroism of our soldiers at the front, the labor of the Uzbek people behind the front, the bravery of women, girls and the elderly to ensure victory were sung.

This image, the plot line related to the fate of Tursunboy among the events are the most impressive and exciting moments of the work.

War Hero Ikromjon Usmanov returned from the front with one leg amputated. After that, they brought the order that had not been handed over to him and presented it solemnly at the meeting. Ikramjon is happy and proud that the country appreciates his services.

Khayolan imagines his son Tursunboy at the front line, on the battlefield. Imagining that overcoats are suitable for his tall and handsome son, he is happy that his son is defending the Motherland in difficult times.

Ikramjon and Jannat have no children except for Tursunboy, so they focus all their hopes on him. The writer emphasizes this situation in several places of the work. Uncle Rayimberdi asked Ikromjon, who had one of his legs amputated: “Didn’t you suffer a lot?”, Ikromjon replied: “I am cutting it so badly that I can see my stupid Tursunboy. It’s like saying, who are you leaving me for? No, I did not die alone, I survived. When I came, he was gone. I couldn’t see the face of our lonesome. May he return safely. If God doesn't show, if something happens to him, I'll be done...” [3] - thus the writer explains to the reader that Tursunboy played a decisive role both in the life of Ikramjon and in the life of aunt Jannat.

Said Ahmad is an advanced writer who has contributed greatly to the development of Uzbek prose with his cheerful, relaxing stories and weighty novels.

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